

AN ALTERNATIVE SCHEME FOR APPROXIMATING A PERIODIC FUNCTION

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ABSTRACT

Fourier series is generally used in applied mathematics and non-linear mechanics to solve the problems containing periodic functions. The aim of this paper is to present a new scheme through involving the Taylor's series after some process modification for all such problems. It will save the long evaluation process involve in computing the different constants of Fourier series. The result obtained by the present method has been compared with the result from the Fourier series expansion w.r.t. the exact solution and found to be more satisfactory.

KEYWORDS

Fourier series, Taylor series, Periodic function, Rest Bounded Variation, Convergence.

1. INTRODUCTION

Infinite series expansion is a practically important method which is generally used to define a function as a series of algebraic terms. Its convergence and divergence depends on the limit of its partial sum. In particular, the series is said to converge to a definite value if the limit of its partial sum exists finitely, otherwise it is called a divergent series. An excellent discussion in this regard along with the condition for its convergence is discussed by Wrede et al [1]. Power series is a form of infinite series which is particularly important to explain an algebraic or non-algebraic function in terms of linear or non-linear polynomial. Mathematically, it consists of the various exponents in the following form,

$$a_0 + a_1x + a_2x^2 + \dots = \sum_n a_n x^n \quad (1.1)$$

where, the various coefficients of x in equation (1.1) may be zero or non-zero constants.

Fourier series and Taylor series expansions are the tools of expanding a non-algebraic function in terms of the respective polynomial addition. Sine and cosine functions due to their repetitive nature, reflects the basic characteristics of Fourier series and making it an important for analysis [2]. It is particularly applied to the problems dealing with wave mechanics where the function assumes a transition state at the end of each interval. Some excellent examples of the application of Fourier series have been given in [3, 4]. In general way, the Fourier series can be determined for the function $f(x)$ by

$$f(x) = a_0 + \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \{a_n \cos nx + b_n \sin nx\} \quad (1.2)$$

where, a_0, a_n, b_n are the coefficients of the sine and cosine terms which can be evaluated by definite integration. Fourier series gives a good fundamental result by giving the complete periodic view of the function through a single relation. However, it still suffers from the following three major problems.

- i. The results predicted by the Fourier series are oscillatory in nature for each point within the interval of given boundary value problem. This is quite opposite to the general expectation of the expecting smooth function.
- ii. The errors given by the Fourier series approximation especially at the end points of the interval is usually noticeable for the finite number of terms in expansion.
- iii. The sharp and sudden transitions due to any point of discontinuity within the given interval cannot be described by it.

Taylor's series on the other hand, is a commonly used power series due to its simple structure and faster convergence as compared to Fourier series for non-periodic, algebraic and transcendental functions particularly of non-trigonometric nature. Different conditions necessary for the convergence of this series have been discussed in [1, 5]. The foremost condition among them is the existence of the continuity of the function & its derivatives in the closed interval.

Above discussion clears that the Taylor's series is a better & comfortable option than the Fourier series for the expansion of a given function. This paper focuses on describing a new scheme that uses Taylor's series approximation to all those periodic functions which are generally approximated by Fourier's formula. For the purpose, we define the function as a series of proper algebraic terms and use the scheme parallel to the case of Cubic spline where each closed sub-interval is defined by a cubic polynomial [6].

2. IMPORTANT DEDUCTIONS

"Rest of Bounded Variation" abbreviated as R_0^+BV forms a sequence of null class $c = \{c_n\}$ of positive numbers which tends to zero as $n \rightarrow \infty$ [7, 8, 9]. Hence, for an element $c \in R_0^+BV$, it shows the following property

$$\sum_{n=m}^{\infty} |c_n - c_{n+1}| \leq K(c) c_m \quad (2.1)$$

for all $m \in N$. Here "K" denotes the positive constant depending on the given value of the parameter c .

R_0^+BV – Sequence plays an important role in establishing many results by defining the boundedness of the net variation in parameter. The useful implications of this sequence can be obtained in many research articles [10, 11].

In this research article, we structured Theorem-2 to shows the important condition for convergence of R_0^+BV – sequence. This result also helps in establishing the convergence of error obtained in the Taylor’s series expansion of a function. Theorem-3 proves an important relation between the terms defining the aberration in Taylor’s series expansion and R_0^+BV – sequence. The n^{th} error term of a sequence is nothing but the remainder term (or simply remainder) in the expansion truncated to “ n ” terms. To prove this result, it is necessary to obtain the class of metric space that defines the error during the expansion of a function by Taylor’s series. This primary result is discussed in Theorem-1.

Theorem 1. Let, Ω be the non-empty set denoting the intensity of aberration in the countable class of error terms during the Taylor series expansion of a function. Then, Ω forms a metric space for the metric defined as $d(\in_x, \in_y) = |\in_x - \in_y|$, where \in_x, \in_y are the two arbitrary elements of Ω .

Proof. The proof of this theorem follows from the fact that Ω denoting the class of error terms in the Taylor series expansion of a function consists of the set of real numbers. Hence, the non-negative number $d(\in_x, \in_y)$ representing the usual “Distance Parameter” on R will represent a usual metric for this class.

Theorem 2. A decreasing R_0^+BV – sequence is convergent.

Proof. Let $C = \{c_n\}$ be the given null sequence of positive numbers in which the partial sum of the terms defining consecutive differences $S_{m,n}$ is defined as,

$$|S_{m,n}| = \sum_{\eta=m}^n |c_\eta - c_{\eta+1}| \tag{2.2}$$

Or,
$$|S_{m,n}| = |c_m - c_{m+1}| + |c_{m+1} - c_{m+2}| + \dots + |c_n - c_{n+1}| \tag{2.3}$$

Clearly,
$$|S_{m,n}| \leq \sum_{\eta=m}^{\infty} |c_\eta - c_{\eta+1}| + \sum_{\eta=m+1}^{\infty} |c_{\eta+1} - c_{\eta+2}| + \dots + \sum_{\eta=n}^{\infty} |c_\eta - c_{\eta+1}| \tag{2.4}$$

Since, $C = \{c_n\}$ forms the R_0^+BV – sequence, the inequality showed in equation (2.1) can be used to obtain the following result from equation (2.4)

$$|S_{m,n}| \leq K_m(c)c_m + K_{m+1}(c)c_{m+1} + K_{m+2}(c)c_{m+2} + \dots + K_n(c)c_n \quad (2.5)$$

$k_i(c), m \leq i \leq n$ is a positive constant, so there must exist $\Xi(c) = \max_{\zeta} \{K_{\zeta}(c)\}$ such that,

$$|S_{m,n}| \leq \Xi(c) \{c_m + c_{m+1} + c_{m+2} + \dots + c_n\} \quad (2.6)$$

But, according to our assumption $\{c_n\}$ is a decreasing sequence of positive numbers $c_1 > c_2 > c_3 > \dots$, so the expression on right hand side of equation (2.6) can be written as,

$$|S_{m,n}| < \Xi(c)(n-m)c_m, \forall n > m \quad (2.7)$$

Choosing $c_m = \frac{1}{(n-m)c_{1m}}$ will convert equation (2.7) to the following form,

$$|S_{m,n}| < \frac{\Xi(c)}{c_{1m}} \quad (2.8)$$

This in turn, assures the required result.

D’Alembert’s ratio test is generally used to estimate the convergence of the given series [1, 12]. It does so by comparing the relative magnitude of successive terms. So, if $\sum u_n$ is a series to be examined for convergence and

$$\rho = \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \left(\frac{u_{n+1}}{u_n} \right) \quad (2.9)$$

be the ratio of consecutive terms, then the series $\sum u_n$ is said to be convergent for $\rho < 1$ and divergent for $\rho > 1$. For the case $\rho = 1$, the behavior of the series is undeterminable by this test. On taking the magnitude of the ratio of terms in equation (2.9), the same test can be applied to test the absolute convergence of the series.

Theorem 3. Errors in the Taylor series expansion of a well defined continuously differentiable function form a R_0^+BV – sequence.

Proof. To prove it, we consider a function $f(x)$ which is continuously differentiable $(n+1)$ times in an open interval containing “a”. If the Taylor series expansion of $f(x)$ is truncated after $(n-1)^{th}$ step, then their difference can be easily obtained to be,

$$\xi_n = f(x) - \left\{ f(a) + (x-a)f'(a) + \frac{(x-a)^2}{2!} f''(a) + \dots + \frac{(x-a)^{n-1}}{(n-1)!} f^{(n-1)}(a) + R_n(x,a) \right\} \quad (2.10)$$

$R_n(x,a) = \frac{(x-a)^n}{n!} f^{(n)}(\Lambda)$ is the remainder term in the expansion of Taylor series and Λ is any point between “ x & a ”. Clearly, $\{\xi_n\}$ will form a null sequence of positive numbers. Therefore, the difference between two terms can be expressed as

$$\xi_{n+1} - \xi_n = \left| \frac{(x-a)^n}{n!} (f^{(n)}(\Lambda) - f^{(n)}(a)) - \frac{(x-a)^{n+1}}{(n+1)!} f^{(n+1)}(\Lambda) \right| \quad (2.11)$$

Defining a metric function for this class of result as,

$$d(\xi_{n+1}, \xi_n) = |\xi_{n+1} - \xi_n| = \kappa_{n+1} \quad (2.12)$$

and applying the D’Alembert’s ratio test to the series $\sum \kappa_n$ through ρ ,

$$\rho = \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \left(\frac{\kappa_{n+1}}{\kappa_n} \right) = \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \frac{\left| \frac{(x-a)^{n+1}}{(n+1)!} (f^{(n+1)}(\Lambda) - f^{(n+1)}(a)) - \frac{(x-a)^{n+2}}{(n+2)!} f^{(n+2)}(\Lambda) \right|}{\left| \frac{(x-a)^n}{n!} (f^{(n)}(\Lambda) - f^{(n)}(a)) - \frac{(x-a)^{n+1}}{(n+1)!} f^{(n+1)}(\Lambda) \right|} \quad (2.13)$$

$$= \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \frac{\left| \frac{(x-a)^{n+1}}{(n+1)!} \left| (f^{(n+1)}(\Lambda) - f^{(n+1)}(a)) - \frac{x-a}{n+2} f^{(n+2)}(\Lambda) \right| \right|}{\left| \frac{(x-a)^n}{n!} \left| (f^{(n)}(\Lambda) - f^{(n)}(a)) - \frac{x-a}{n+1} f^{(n+1)}(\Lambda) \right| \right|} \quad (2.14)$$

f is a continuously differentiable function. So, it must have a well defined existence. Also equation (2.14) yields $\rho \rightarrow 0 (< 1)$ as $n \rightarrow \infty$. So, in accordance to D’Alembert’s ratio test, the series $\sum \kappa_n$ converges absolutely.

Further, we have
$$\sum_{n=m}^{\infty} |\xi_{n+1} - \xi_n| \leq \sum \kappa_n \tag{2.15}$$

which can be written alternatively as,

$$\sum_{n=m}^{\infty} |\xi_{n+1} - \xi_n| \leq \left(\sum \frac{\kappa_n}{\epsilon_m} \right) \epsilon_m \tag{2.16}$$

The convergence of $\sum \kappa_n$ confirms the convergence and existence of the series $\left(\sum \frac{\kappa_n}{\epsilon_m} \right)$ that suffices the condition for proving the necessary result of this theorem.

Theorem-3 gives the condition for boundness in the absolute error during the Taylor series expansion of a function with respect to the original value. Since, the error terms in the Taylor's expansion of a continuously differentiable function form a decreasing sequence. So in accordance to Theorem-2 they will converge, thereby giving an alternative necessary condition to prove the convergence of the Taylor's series.

3. PRELIMINARY PRINCIPLE OF THE NEW METHOD

Consider a periodic function $f(x)$ in the closed interval $I = [a, b]$. Using Taylor's theorem, we can estimate this function in terms of another function "F",

$$f(x) = F(x - [m]h) \tag{3.1}$$

With,
$$m = \frac{x - a}{h} \tag{3.2}$$

The bracket [] denoting the "Greatest Integer Function" can be used to express the *point of inflection* in characterizing the graph of a function. Literally, it is the point at which the direction of concavity of the graph changes [12].

Characterizing the inflexion by substituting $f''(a) = 0$ in the error term defined by equation (2.10) we get,

$$\epsilon_{n_1} = f(x) - \left\{ f(a) + (x-a)f'(a) + \frac{(x-a)^3}{3!} f'''(a) + \dots + \frac{(x-a)^n}{n!} f^{(n)}(a) \right\} \tag{3.3}$$

and so the new sequence $\{\epsilon_{n_i}\}$ will form an open bound for $\{\epsilon_n\}$. In order to avoid the mismatching of the results predicted by the Taylor's theorem at the point of inflexion, some process modification is made. However, it is known that Taylor's theorem provides the best result when the number of terms "n" in expansion is more. In order to minimize the number of terms in expansion and increasing the exactness in result, a multiple expansion of function from one inflexion point to another is necessary.

In this way, let us subdivide the interval $[a, b]$ by an ordered set of points "P" called partition as,

$$P = \{y_0, y_1, y_2, \dots, y_n\} \tag{3.4}$$

and assuming the various sub-intervals from $a = y_0 \leq y_1 \leq y_2 \dots \leq y_n = b$ like $[a, y_1), [y_1, y_2), [y_2, y_3), \dots, [y_{n-1}, b]$. The function $F(X)$ given in equation (3.1) for the domain $[y_i, y_{i+1})$ is further approximated through algebraic polynomial obtained by applying Taylor series about the inflexion point $X = X_i$,

$$F([y_i, y_{i+1})) = F_i(X_i + x) \tag{3.5}$$

Clearly, the function $F(X)$ for the interval "T" will be the union of all the functions in the various sub-intervals i.e.

$$F(X) = \bigcup_{i=1}^n F([y_i, y_{i+1})) \tag{3.6}$$

In this way, multiple results are required for expressing a periodic function.

4. NUMERICAL RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The following examples illustrate the results obtained by the proposed method to solve the periodic functions. At the same time the result of Fourier series are considered to compare the efficiency and accuracy of the proposed method. The examples selected for present study have the functions of three particular from:

- i. Function of purely trigonometric form.
- ii. Function of transcendental form.
- iii. Function of purely algebraic form.

4.1 Illustrative Examples

Example 1. Consider the following equation

$$f(x) = \sin x \text{ in the interval } (0, 2\pi) \tag{4.1}$$

Clearly, we have $a = 0$, $b = 2\pi$ and the point of inflexion in the open interval $(0, 2\pi)$ is π . In lieu of this inflexion, we will use the proposed expansion for the sub-intervals $(0, \pi)$ & $[\pi, 2\pi)$.

In present case, the Taylor series has been expanded up to first four non-zero terms of the formula. A comparison between the results between Fourier formula and proposed formula is made with respect to the exact results and illustrated in Figure-1. The curve clearly shows that the results predicted by the proposed formula are in close proximity to the actual results.

Example 2. Consider the equation which is a special case of the problem discussed in [13]

$$f(x) = e^x \text{ in the interval } (-\pi, \pi) \tag{4.2}$$

The Fourier expansion of this function is,

$$f(x) = \frac{\sinh \pi}{\pi} + \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{2(-1)^n \sinh \pi}{\pi(1+n^2)} (\cos nx - n \sin nx) \tag{4.3}$$

Here, we have $a = -\pi$, $b = \pi$. There is no point of inflexion in the given interval.

Fig.1 Comparison between Actual Results, Results by Fourier Formula and by the Proposed Formula for $f(x) = \sin x$.

On using Taylor series and Fourier series expansion for the given function by expanding it to first five non-zero terms of the expansion, we obtain the result as shown in Figure-2. The plot clearly shows that proposed formula retraces the actual plot with lesser deviation than the Fourier series expansion.

Example 3. Consider the equation

$$f(x) = x + x^2 \text{ in the interval } (-\pi, \pi) \tag{4.4}$$

The Fourier expansion for this function obtains to be,

$$f(x) = \frac{\pi^2}{3} + \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} (-1)^n \frac{2}{n} \left\{ \frac{2}{n} \cos nx - \sin nx \right\} \tag{4.5}$$

For the proposed formula we chose two sub-intervals $(0, \pi)$ & $[\pi, 2\pi)$.

Based on the Taylor series to first two terms of the expansion and Fourier series expansion up to first four terms, the comparison has been made and illustrated in Figure-3. This again shows that the proposed method works very well in present case.

Fig.2 Comparison between Actual Results, Results by Fourier Formula and by the Proposed Formula for $f(x) = e^x$.

Fig.3 Comparison between Actual Results, Results by Fourier Formula and by the Proposed Formula for $f(x) = x + x^2$.

5. CONCLUSION

Various results shown in the figures clearly demonstrate that the proposed strategy gives a good and in fact superior result as compared to the Fourier Formula for periodic as well as non-periodic functions. This also reduces the long calculation work involved in establishing the Fourier Formula for the particular problem.

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